

1 **Original Research**

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4 **Genetic relationship between Neck and Limb defects in Pura Raza Española Horses.**

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29 **Summary**

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- 31 • **Background:** Defects affecting the horse's neck and limb conformation can negatively
 - 32 impact a horse's performance and suitability for equestrian activities.
 - 33 • **Objectives:** to assess the prevalence of the simultaneous occurrence of defects in the
 - 34 limbs and neck and to estimate the genetic correlations between these defects
 - 35 • **Study design:** Retrospective cohort study.
 - 36 • **Methods:** Prevalence and genetic correlations between 12 conformational limb defects
 - 37 and 2 neck defects were analyzed in 56644 Pura Raza Española horses. Different
 - 38 approaches were used: A) two-class for neck and limb defects (0-no defect, 1-presence
 - 39 of defect); B) three-class for limb defects (0-no defect, 1-slight defect, 2-serious defect)
 - 40 and four-class for neck defects (0-no defect, 1-slight defect, 2-serious defect, 3-
 - 41 disqualifying defect). Genetic correlations between conformational defects were
 - 42 estimated using a multivariate animal model within a Bayesian framework with the
 - 43 BLUPF90 software family, including age as a covariate, and gender, coat color,
 - 44 management of breeder's stud farm and inbreeding as fixed effects
 - 45 • **Results:** The most prevalent limb defect in horses affected with Cresty neck (CN) and
 - 46 Ewe neck (EN) was Splay-footed rear limb (SFR) (80.2% and 72.5%, respectively).
 - 47 The genetic correlations ranged from -0.22 ± 0.090 for EN- SFR to 0.44 ± 0.123 for CN-
 - 48 Divergent hock, and in approach B, -0.25 ± 0.028 for CN-Convergent hock to 0.51 ± 0.228
 - 49 for CN- Splay-footed forelimb
 - 50 • **Main limitations:** The veterinarians responsible for evaluating the horses are unknown.
 - 51 Data were only collected once during the animal's lifetime, making it impossible to
 - 52 determine how the defects evolved over time.
 - 53 • **Conclusions:** This study revealed a moderate relationship between limb and neck
 - 54 defects, emphasizing the need for meticulous planning to improve these defects in the
 - 55 PRE breed.

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59 **1. Introduction**

60 Among the various aspects of equine anatomy, the neck plays a fundamental role, as it
61 not only influences the animal's aesthetics but can also have significant implications for its
62 functionality and overall well-being (1,2), as well as affecting its economic depreciation.

63 Conformation defects in the neck, can have broader repercussions, affecting the
64 alignment and functionality of the limbs (1–3). Cresty neck (CN), characterized by an abnormal
65 curvature in the cervical region (3–5) causes an alteration in neck posture, which can change
66 the way the horse distributes its weight and pressure throughout its body. CN is also associated
67 with metabolic problems related to excessive weight (3,6,7). Recently, heavy birth weight has
68 been associated with a tendency towards offset carpi (8), suggesting that early developmental
69 factors also play a role in the emergence of limb deformities. Ewe neck (EN), characterized by
70 excessive length and a low position of the neck (2), could also negatively affect limb
71 conformation. Both deformities can create additional strain on the bone and muscle structure,
72 primarily affecting the limbs due to the altered weight distribution and movement mechanics.
73 Horses with neck deformities may also experience a decrease in their ability to perform smooth,
74 balanced movements, leading to uneven wear on joints and bones. This can result in irregular
75 muscle development supporting the limbs, exacerbating issues such as hock deviations, knee
76 deformities, or wear on the fetlocks (9).

77 The relationship between neck abnormalities and limbs joint deformities in horses has
78 never been studied in depth, but this study is a pioneer in this field. Therefore, analyzing the
79 relationship between these defects is essential for an accurate assessment of equine health, the
80 prevention of related issues, and the implementation of effective strategies to maintain the
81 structural integrity of the horse.

82 Therefore, the main objectives of this work are to assess the prevalence of the
83 simultaneous occurrence of various conformational defects in the limbs and neck in a

84 significant population of PRE horses, and to estimate the genetic correlations between these
85 defects, with the aim of reducing their prevalence in the breed or potentially eliminating their
86 incidence within the population.

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88 **2. Materials and methods**

89 *2.1 Data set*

90 The database comprising a total of 56644 Pura Raza Español Horses (PRE) (18562
91 males and 38082 females), with a limb conformation defect of any kind. The average age at
92 evaluation was 5.17 ± 2.29 years. Data collection occurred between the years 2012 and 2023,
93 during the mandatory morphological assessment, a prerequisite for official registration in the
94 PRE stud book (10). This assessment was carried out by 12 specialized veterinarians trained in
95 standardized aptitude testing for this breed, with each horse evaluated by a single assessor. To
96 assess conformational defects phenotypically, the horses were observed standing on a stable,
97 level surface, with the limbs naturally positioned. The fore and hind limbs were aligned as
98 parallel and perpendicular as possible, with the hooves aligned. If doubts persisted about a
99 conformational limb defect while the horse was stationary. Importantly, no sedatives were
100 administered during the evaluation process.

101 The dataset encompassed two types of neck defects (cresty neck -CN-; and ewe neck -
102 EN-; Figure 1), and various conformational limb traits: Forelimb defects (Buck knee -BUK-;
103 Calf knee -CK-; Bench knee -BEK-; Knock knee -KK-; Splay-footed forelimb -SFF-; Pigeon-
104 toed forelimb -PTF-; Figure 2), and rear limb defects (Closed hock -CH-; Open hock -OH-;
105 Convergent hock -CVH-; Divergent hock -DVH-; Splay-footed rear limb -SFR-; Pigeon-toed
106 rear limb -PTR-; Figure 3).

107 To ascertain conformational limb defects and their severity, the study employed a
108 method known as lines of aplomb. These lines are imaginary vertical markers originating from

109 specific anatomical landmarks. In the forelimbs, they begin at the outer edge of the shoulder
110 joint and the humeroulnar joint, extending downwards to the ground surface. Similarly, in the
111 forelimbs, lines of aplomb originate from the highest point of the buttock and the coxofemoral
112 joint, reaching down to the ground surface.

113 This study employed two distinct approaches:

114 **Approach A-** Neck defects and conformational limbs defects were scored as
115 dichotomic traits (0-no defect, 1- defect present).

116 **Approach B-** Neck defects and conformational limb defects were scored on a
117 categorical scale, using a three-class scale for limb defects (0- no defect, 1- slight defect, 2-
118 serious defect) and a four-class scale for neck defects (0- no defect, 1- slight defect, 2- serious
119 defect, 3- disqualifying defect). For neck defects, class 3 was disqualifying; however, this class
120 was not assigned to limb defects, as a horse cannot be disqualified for such defects in the PRE.

121 *2.2. Genetic and Statistical analysis*

122 A Maximum-Likelihood Chi-square test was conducted to compare the probabilities of the
123 presence or absence of neck defects in horses with limb conformation defects, using the
124 function 'chisq.test' from the 'stats' package in R (11).

125 Multivariate animal genetic models were used to estimate the genetic correlations between
126 conformational defects in the limbs and neck. Forelimb and rear limb defects were analyzed in
127 combination with CN and separately with EN for each approach (A and B). Therefore, a total
128 of four genetic models were developed for this analysis. The equation in matrix notation used
129 to solve the mixed models was:

$$130 \quad \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{e}$$

$$131 \quad \mathbf{u} \sim N(0, \mathbf{A}\sigma_u^2), \mathbf{e} \sim N(0, \mathbf{I}\sigma_e^2)$$

132 where \mathbf{y} is the vector of observations, \mathbf{X} is the incidence matrix of fixed effects, \mathbf{Z} is the
133 incidence matrix of the animal genetic effect, \mathbf{b} is the vector of fixed effects, \mathbf{u} is the vector of

134 the direct animal genetic effect, \mathbf{e} is the vector of residuals, σ_u^2 is the direct additive genetic
135 variance, σ_e^2 is the residual variance, \mathbf{I} is an identity matrix, and \mathbf{A} is the numerator relationship
136 matrix.

137 The genetic parameters were estimated using the Blupf90 software family (12). A
138 Bayesian approach with threshold models was applied using the GIBBSF90+ program. A total
139 of 250,000 iterations were performed, with the first 50,000 being considered as burn-in, after
140 which, every 1st sample was saved. In all, 200,000 iterations were available for a post Gibbs
141 analysis. Convergence was tested using Monte Carlo sampling error, computed by time-series
142 procedures (13). Finally, a post-Gibbs analysis was performed using POSTGIBBSF90 (14) to
143 compute posterior means, additive and residual variances, and the standard deviations. To
144 identify the precision of the parameters, the 95% highest posterior density intervals were
145 determined from their marginal posterior distributions.

146 In the genetic model, the age at assessment (in years: 2–18 years) was included as a
147 linear covariate. The fixed effects included in the model were: sex (2 levels: male and female),
148 coat color (2 levels: grey and non-grey) (15), management of breeder's stud farm (3 levels:
149 intensive management, in which horses are kept in stables and primarily fed with compound
150 feed and straw; mixed management, combining stabling and feeding based on compound feed
151 and natural forage but with limited access to pasture; semi-extensive Management, in which
152 the horse has unlimited access to natural pastures although the animals also are kept in stables)
153 and the classic inbreeding coefficient -F- (3 levels: $\leq 6.25\%$, $> 6.25\%$ to $< 12.50\%$, $\geq 12.50\%$).
154 The F value, defined as the probability that the two alleles at any locus in an individual are
155 identical by descent (16)(Wright, 1922), was computed using Endog software (v.3.0) (17). All
156 the factors included in the model turned out to be significant for most defects (data not shown).

157 A Multivariate Generalized Non-linear Model (GLZ) with a multinomial logit
158 distribution was employed to investigate significant associations between conformational

159 limb's defects and neck defects, and the effects of their potential influencing factors. All the
160 statistical analyses were conducted using the function 'glm' from the 'stats' package in R for the
161 analysis of approach A and the function 'polr' from the 'MASS' in R to analyze approach B
162 (11).

163 For the genetic evaluations, the genealogical information was obtained from the PRE
164 StudBook (18), ensuring a minimum of 5 known generations. The pedigree file comprised a
165 total of 106971 individuals.

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167 **3. Results**

168 Concerning the forelimbs, the records presented 2819 horses affected with BUK; 12995
169 with CK; 1570 with BEK; 14569 with KK; 44545 with SFR; and 466 with PTR. As regards the
170 rear limbs, 9435 horses presented CH; 15091 OH; 38068 CVH; 3575 DVH; 11978 SFF; and
171 10614 PTF (see Supplementary Tables 1 & 2).

172 The number and proportions of PRE horses affected and unaffected by neck and limb
173 defects are presented in Tables 1. In PRE, the most prevalent forelimb defects that occur
174 alongside a neck defect are KK (37.8% with CN and 34.1% with EN); SFF (34.5% with CN
175 and 32.0% with EN), and PTF (31.6% with CN and 26.6% with EN). In contrast, the forelimb
176 defects that appear less frequently in conjunction with neck defects are BUK (8.1% with CN
177 and 7.4% with EN) and BEK (5.8% with CN and 4.4% with EN). All the differences between
178 the proportions were statistically significant ($P < 0.001$).

179 The most prevalent rear limb defects that occur alongside a neck defect are SFR (80.2%
180 with CN and 72.5% with EN), and CVH (62.6% with CN and 66.1% with EN). Conversely, the
181 rear limb defects that appear less frequently in conjunction with neck defects are CH (24.8%
182 with CN and 25.2% with EN) and PTR (5.0% with CN and 4.3% with EN). It is important to
183 highlight that the percentage of animals affected by decreases in CVH in the presence of any

184 neck defect. Similarly, the occurrence of OH decreases when the CN defect is present, and the
185 number of SFR cases decline in the presence of the EN defect. All the differences between the
186 proportions were statistically significant ($P<0.001$), except for the SFR defect in combination
187 with CN and PTR in combination with EN.

188 Table 2 shows the genetic correlations between neck defects and conformation (fore and
189 rear limbs) based on the two approaches carried out. The higher-value positive genetic
190 correlations found between neck defects and conformational forelimb defects in PRE for KK
191 and SFF. For KK, the genetic correlations are positive and significant in both approaches: in
192 Approach A, the genetic correlation with CN is 0.28 ± 0.022 , and 0.12 ± 0.046 for EN, while in
193 Approach B, the correlations increase slightly, reaching 0.32 ± 0.029 for CN and 0.26 ± 0.052 for
194 EN. For SFF, the genetic correlation with CN is 0.14 ± 0.095 and 0.18 ± 0.082 for EN in Approach
195 A, while in Approach B, the correlations increase, reaching 0.51 ± 0.228 for CN and 0.28 ± 0.073
196 for EN. Positive genetic correlations were also observed for Approach B between CN and CK
197 (0.11 ± 0.037), BEK (0.16 ± 0.060), and PTF (0.26 ± 0.086). For the remaining genetic
198 correlations, there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a genetic relationship
199 between the traits, as the HPD 0.95 intervals included zero.

200 The higher-value positive genetic correlations were found between neck defects and
201 conformational rear limb defects in PRE horses for DVH and PTR. For DVH, the genetic
202 correlations were positive in both approaches: in Approach A, the genetic correlation with CN
203 was 0.44 ± 0.123 , while with EN it was 0.20 ± 0.029 . In Approach B, the correlations were
204 slightly lower for CN, reaching 0.38 ± 0.030 , and slightly lower for EN at 0.19 ± 0.032 . For PTR,
205 the genetic correlations were positive, although more moderate: in Approach A, the genetic
206 correlation with EN was 0.22 ± 0.135 , whereas in Approach B, increased, reaching 0.26 ± 0.209
207 for CN and 0.16 ± 0.050 for EN.

208 The most notable negative genetic correlations between neck defects and
209 conformational rear limb defects in PRE were observed for OH, CVH, and SFR. For OH, the
210 genetic correlation with CN in Approach B was -0.16 ± 0.036 , while for CVH, in Approach B,
211 the correlation was -0.25 ± 0.028 for CN and -0.09 ± 0.026 for EN. For SFR, negative genetic
212 correlations were observed with EN in both approaches: in Approach A, the correlation with
213 EN was -0.22 ± 0.090 , while and in Approach B, it was -0.15 ± 0.033 .

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215 **4. Discussion**

216 The conformation of an animal, particularly the equine species, plays a critical role in
217 ensuring biomechanical efficiency and reducing the likelihood of injury (19). This concept is
218 fundamental in evaluating the functional performance of horses, where deviations in
219 conformation often lead to excessive stress on limbs and joints (20,21). As a result, a holistic
220 evaluation of conformation is essential, as deviations in one area, such as the neck, may affect
221 the function of the limbs, thus increasing the risk of long-term damage (22).

222 Cervical dysfunction may contribute to altered gait and biomechanics of the forelimb
223 and trunk, highlighting the intricate relationship between the neck and limb function (23). In
224 addition, radiological abnormalities in the caudal cervical vertebrae have been associated with
225 neck stiffness (decreased range of motion), thoracic limb lameness (24–27), and ataxia (28),
226 suggesting a broad impact of cervical issues on overall equine mobility. The functional interplay
227 between neck and limb conformation is further supported by the theory of alloydism, which
228 suggests that defects in one body region can lead to compensatory problems in another (29).
229 According to Peña et al. (30), the balance or harmony between body regions is crucial for
230 maintaining correct conformation and functional performance in horses.

231 Biomechanically, the position and movement of the neck also play a critical role in
232 determining the load distribution across the forelimbs and rear limbs, particularly during

233 activities such as trot and back movements. Numerous studies have demonstrated the influence
234 of the head-neck position on equine movement and limb kinematics (31–34). Incorrect head-
235 neck positioning can lead to uneven loading across the limbs, thus increasing the risk of injury
236 (22). Additionally, the large dorsal and ventral muscles, along with the ligamentum nuchae,
237 contribute significantly to energy storage and coordination during movement, linking neck
238 conformation directly to limb performance (35,36).

239 The results from Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the prevalence of
240 forelimb and rear limb deformities in PRE horses, classified by the presence of neck
241 abnormalities such as CN and EN. Horses with CN or EN exhibit significantly higher
242 prevalences of forelimb defects, particularly KK and SFF. The KK defect is one of the most
243 prevalent knee defects in the PRE horse population, with a prevalence of 26.5% (37), while the
244 SFF defect, although not the most prevalent angular hoof deviation in the PRE population, has
245 nevertheless a reported prevalence of 26.6% (38). The results in this study point to a higher
246 prevalence of both forelimb defects in horses exhibiting a neck defect. These findings are
247 consistent with studies that have shown how abnormalities in neck conformation can negatively
248 influence the biomechanics of the forelimbs, increasing stress on joints and heightening the risk
249 of musculoskeletal disorders (39).

250 Table 1 highlights the prevalence of rear limb deformities, including SFR and CVH,
251 among horses with neck defects. Studies have shown that neck misalignment can lead to
252 compensatory movements in the rear limbs, particularly as horses attempt to distribute their
253 weight more evenly during movement (27).

254 Witte and Hunt (40) pointed out that limb alignment in horses is genetically determined
255 at birth but can be influenced by external factors such as the mare's health and nutrition. They
256 explain that foals with misaligned postures place uneven pressure on their growth plates
257 (physes), which can lead to conditions like physitis and disrupt the process of endochondral

258 ossification. Although angular limb deformities are known to result from a combination of
259 genetic and environmental factors influencing a horse's growth and conformation during
260 development, to date, no specific studies have investigated the genetic correlations between
261 them. We focused our analysis on exploring these correlations, as shown in Table 2. Approach
262 B (three levels for limb defects and four levels for neck traits) is the most suitable model, as it
263 fits the data better, appropriately penalizes complexity (as evidenced by significantly lower DIC
264 values), and provides deeper insights into the genetic relationships between neck and limb traits.
265 This confirms the findings of Ripollés-Lobo et al. (3), who noted that models with three to five
266 classes are more accurate for estimating orthopedic deformity parameters.

267 The higher number of positive correlations found between specific forelimb defects with
268 both neck conformation traits suggests that neck defects are more strongly associated with
269 forelimb deformities. Specifically, limb defects that are most prevalent alongside the CN defect
270 also show high prevalence with the EN defect. These correlations reveal that horses with certain
271 neck conformation defects are genetically predisposed to specific limb deformities, and that
272 selective breeding focused on improving neck conformation could help reduce the incidence of
273 these defects.

274 In the literature, no studies have been found that genetically correlate neck defects with
275 limb defects. However, there are numerous studies that, using a linear scale, genetically
276 correlate variables related to neck shape with those of the limbs. In this regard, Perdomo-
277 González et al (41), indicate a genetic correlation of 0.70 between neck length and knee
278 perimeter in Pura Raza Menorquina horses. Sánchez-Guerrero et al. (10,42) also found a genetic
279 correlation of 0.54 between neck length and cannon bone circumference, of 0.14 between upper
280 neck line and lateral knee angle, of 0.28 between upper neck line and frontal knee angle and of
281 0.42 between neck length and knee angle in PRE. Magnusson (43) demonstrated a genetic
282 correlation of 0.38 between neck length and forelimb defects, particularly closed hocks in

283 Standardbred Trotters. Additionally, Novotna et al. (44,45) found that the neck position in
284 Czech Warmbloods was positively correlated with croup shape (0.22), front hoof (0.11), hind
285 hoof (0.27) and stride length at trot (0.32). De Oliverira et al. (46) found a genetic correlation
286 of 0.71 between neck length and limb length, and of 0.41 between neck length and cannon girth
287 in Campolina horses. The genetic correlations identified in the PRE (10) between the upper
288 neck line and the hock from the rear (0.18), as well as between the upper neck line and the
289 lateral hock rear (0.14), are lower than those observed in the forelimbs. Folla et al. (47), in
290 Italian Heavy Draught Horses observed negative correlations between upper line length and
291 certain angular deformities in the rear limbs (-0.17), highlighting the genetic influence of neck
292 conformation on limb health.

293 In general, our work has shown that numerous stance defects are moderately correlated
294 with neck conformation defects. This finding aligns with previous authors who have studied
295 the relationships between neck variables and limb variables, thereby underscoring the
296 importance of neck conformation in determining the functionality and coordination of the
297 limbs.

298 **5. Conclusion**

299 The results demonstrate that Pura Raza Española (PRE) horses with conformational
300 limb defects are more likely to also present neck defects, underscoring the critical role of neck
301 conformation in influencing both forelimb and rear limb deformities. Overall, from the
302 perspective of genetic selection aimed at improving the PRE horse population, efforts should
303 focus on minimizing the incidence of the KK, SFF, and DVH defects, which therefore represent
304 a key target in selection programs. This interrelationship suggests a shared genetic
305 predisposition that affects both cervical and limb conformation, substantially impacting the
306 health and competitive performance of the animals. Understanding these correlations is
307 fundamental for designing breeding programs aimed at reducing the prevalence of these defects,

308 thereby ensuring a healthier and more functional equine population. Additionally, it will enable
309 breeders to make more informed decisions to minimize the incidence of these defects in future
310 generations.

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333 **Table 1.**

334 Number and proportions of Pura Raza Española with fore and rear limb conformation defects,
 335 classified by the presence or absence of neck defects. The p-value obtained from a frequency
 336 comparison analysis (Maximum-Likelihood Chi-square test) is shown.

Defects	Cresty Neck			Ewe Neck			
	N Unaffected (%)	N Affected (%)	p value	N Unaffected (%)	N Affected (%)	p value	
Forelimb conformation defects	BUK	2151 (6.1)	668 (8.1)	<0.0001	2021 (6.2)	798 (7.4)	<0.0001
	CK	9832 (22.9)	3159 (29.3)	<0.0001	9367 (23.3)	3620 (26.5)	<0.0001
	BEK	1148 (3.3)	421 (5.8)	<0.0001	1143 (3.5)	422 (4.4)	<0.05
	KK	10396 (23.6)	4170 (37.8)	<0.0001	9783 (23.8)	4783 (34.1)	<0.0001
	SFF	8948 (24.0)	3028 (34.5)	<0.0001	8268 (24.0)	3706 (32.0)	<0.0001
	PTF	7949 (21.9)	2664 (31.6)	<0.0001	7750 (22.9)	2861 (26.6)	<0.0001
Rear limb conformation defects	CH	7278 (22.2)	2155 (24.8)	<0.0001	6819 (21.8)	2608 (25.2)	<0.0001
	OH	12334 (32.5)	2756 (29.7)	<0.0001	10977 (31.0)	4114 (34.7)	<0.0001
	CVH	31847 (73.9)	6216 (62.6)	<0.0001	29542 (73.6)	8518 (66.1)	<0.0001
	DVH	2059 (15.4)	1516 (29.0)	<0.0001	2015 (16.0)	1560 (26.3)	<0.0001
	SFR	35463 (79.1)	9077 (80.2)	>0.05	34197 (81.7)	10341 (72.5)	<0.0001
	PTR	347 (3.6)	119 (5.0)	<0.05	290 (3.6)	176 (4.3)	>0.05

337 N: Number; CH: Closed hock; OH: Open hock; CVH: Convergent hock; DVH: Divergent hock;
 338 SFR: Splay-footed rear limb; PTR: Pigeon-toed rear limb; BUK: Buck knee; CK: Calf knee;
 339 BEK: Bench knee; KK: Knock knee; SFF: Splay-footed forelimb; PTF: Pigeon-toed forelimb.
 340 Horses with conformational limb defects are classified into categories 1 and 2, while horses
 341 with neck defects are classified into classes 1, 2, and 3, with class 3 being considered a criterion
 342 for disqualification. The hypothesis test of proportions was conducted using relative
 343 frequencies.

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347 **Table 2.**

348 Genetic correlations (standard deviations) between conformational fore and rear limb defects

349 and neck defects of Pura Raza Española horses for both approaches.

Defects	Genetic correlations (s.d.)	Approach A (2 clases)		Approach B (3 clases)		
		Cresty Neck	Ewe Neck	Cresty Neck	Ewe Neck	
Forelimb conformation defects	BUK	r_g (s.d.)	-0.02±0.222	0.07±0.056	-0.02±0.079	-0.05±0.087
		HPD 0.95	-0.46 , 0.32	-0.05 , 0.18	-0.16 , 0.12	-0.24 , 0.09
	CK	r_g (s.d.)	-0.13±0.228	-0.07±0.047	0.11±0.037	-0.01±0.034
		HPD 0.95	-0.53 , 0.17	-0.15 , 0.01	0.03 , 0.18	-0.07 , 0.06
	BEK	r_g (s.d.)	-0.01±0.221	-0.02±0.092	0.16±0.060	0.11±0.083
		HPD 0.95	-0.40 , 0.37	-0.21 , 0.16	0.03 , 0.27	-0.05 , 0.29
	KK	r_g (s.d.)	0.28±0.022	0.12±0.046	0.32±0.029	0.26±0.052
		HPD 0.95	0.22 , 0.39	0.04 , 0.19	0.26 , 0.37	0.17 , 0.37
	SFF	r_g (s.d.)	0.14±0.095	0.18±0.082	0.51±0.228	0.28±0.073
		HPD 0.95	0.01 , 0.34	0.02 , 0.35	0.25 , 0.85	0.17 , 0.41
	PTF	r_g (s.d.)	0.08±0.133	-0.06±0.085	0.26±0.086	0.08±0.032
		HPD 0.95	-0.30 , 0.33	-0.20 , 0.13	0.14 , 0.42	0.01 , 0.13
	DIC		-1268895.9	-699097.4	-1653501.5	-1684275.1
	Rear limb conformation defects	CH	r_g (s.d.)	0.08±0.084	-0.01±0.153	0.11±0.034
HPD 0.95			-0.07 , 0.26	-0.23 , 0.42	0.04 , 0.17	-0.08 , 0.05
OH		r_g (s.d.)	-0.11±0.066	0.07±0.102	-0.16±0.036	0.03±0.037
		HPD 0.95	-0.20 , 0.01	-0.08 , 0.24	-0.23 , -0.09	-0.05 , 0.09
CVH		r_g (s.d.)	-0.32 ±0.158	-0.02±0.391	-0.25±0.028	-0.09±0.026
		HPD 0.95	-0.64 , 0.04	-0.42 , 0.95	-0.31 , -0.19	-0.15 , -0.03
DVH		r_g (s.d.)	0.44±0.123	0.20±0.029	0.38±0.030	0.19±0.032
		HPD 0.95	0.18 , 0.66	0.05 , 0.23	0.31 , 0.43	0.12 , 0.25
SFR		r_g (s.d.)	-0.01±0.110	-0.22±0.090	0.01±0.112	-0.15±0.033
		HPD 0.95	-0.18 , 0.26	-0.39 , -0.08	-0.18 , 0.16	-0.21 , -0.07
PTR		r_g (s.d.)	0.10±0.164	0.22±0.135	0.26±0.209	0.16±0.050
		HPD 0.95	-0.27 , 0.53	0.04 , 0.44	0.01 , 0.60	0.07 , 0.25
DIC			-1896706.9	-1293389.2	-2100024.9	-1972272.8

350 r_g : Genetic correlations; s.d.: standard deviations; HPD 0.95: Highest Posterior Density Interval
351 at 95%; DIC: Deviance information criterion; BUK: Buck knee; CK: Calf knee; BEK: Bench
352 knee; KK: Knock knee; SFF: Splay-footed forelimb; PTF: Pigeon-toed forelimb.

353 CH: Closed hock; OH: Open hock; CVH: Convergent hock; DVH: Divergent hock; SFR:

354 Splay-footed rear limb; PTR: Pigeon-toed rear limb.

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357

358 **Figure 1.** Graphic description of the neck defects studied in the Pura Raza Española horse
 359 population, along with an explanation of the assessment scale, which ranges from 0 to 3.

Class 0 (correct)	Cresty neck Class 3 (disqualifying)	Ewe neck Class 3 (disqualifying)

360

361

362 **Figure 2.** Graphic description of the six forelimb conformation defects studied in the Pura Raza
 363 Española horse population, along with an explanation of the assessment scale, which ranges
 364 from 0 to 2.

Class 0 (correct)	Defect	Class 2 (serious)	Defect	Class 2 (serious)

365

366

367 **Figure 3.** Graphic description of the six rear limb conformation defects studied in the Pura Raza
 368 Española horse population, along with an explanation of the assessment scale, which ranges
 369 from 0 to 2.

370

Class 0 (correct)	Defect	Class 2 (serious)	Defect	Class 2 (serious)

371

Table Supplementary 1.

372 Number of Pura Raza Española horses according to the combination of the class conformational

374 forelimb defects (Class 0, 1, 2) and neck defects (Class 0, 1, 2, 3).

Table Supplementary 2.

376 Number of Pura Raza Española horses according to the combination of the class of

377 conformational rear limb defects (Class 0, 1, 2) and neck defects (Class

378

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